

Mutual Coupling Correction Factor for Optimized Multi-Axis Shielded Loop Antenna Magnetic Field Measurements

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Abstract— Standard measurement procedures CISPR 36 for magnetic field measurements below 30 MHz is time consuming. To maintain realistic measurement time, standards limit the amount of the measurement positions and antennas orientations as well as evaluation of the operational modes of the electric vehicle being tested. This paper introduces a multi-axis shielded loop antenna (MSLA) for magnetic field measurements below 30 MHz, proposing a new measurement approach that evaluates all three orientations simultaneously, significantly reducing the required time. The proposed methodology employs multi-channel time-domain measurements, providing access to all three axes simultaneously. The paper thoroughly analyses the effects of the MSLA construction on the measurement results under the influence of the mutual coupling effect between the antennas. The available phase information from each measurement axis due to the proposed measurement method is used to utilize the mutual coupling correction factor. Altogether, the novel multi-axis measurement setup with the provided mutual coupling correction factor can greatly improve measurement accuracy of the MSLA and drastically reduce standard measurement time.

Index Terms— Electromagnetic compatibility, multichannel digitizer, multi-axis antenna, time-domain measurements, mutual-coupling correction factor, phase shift, magnetic loop antenna.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing complexity of electrical equipment, it has been revealed that conventional measurement procedures, such as CISPR 36 [1] and AECTP 500 [2], Edition F which soon will be published, for magnetic field measurements below 30 MHz, can underestimate the highest magnetic field levels due to their measurement method [3]. The high costs of such

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measurements, which require expensive facilities and instrumentation, the standard is balancing time efficiency with measurement accuracy. In the case of CISPR 36, limitations arise from the measurement positions around an electric vehicle (EV) and the evaluations of operational modes to maintain a realistic measurement time [4]. One of the time-consuming issues is related to the use of a single shielded loop antenna (SLA) during measurements. The use of a single SLA significantly increases the measurement time, as the procedure requires to measure EUT from 4 measurement positions in a several antennas orientations to it [5]. In combination with the standard measurement technique, the total measurement time can reach 5-6 hours, even with the implementation of the pre-scan method introduced in the latest CISPR 36 revision [5].

To address the issue of using a single SLA in the measurement procedure, an optimization approach was explored by integrating a MSLA capable of evaluating all required antenna orientations from the single measurement position simultaneously [6], [7]. The design of this antenna is shown in Fig. 1. The integration of a MSLA with a multichannel digitizer has demonstrated a high correlation in measurement results when compared to a single SLA with an conventional super-

Fig. 1 Multi-axis shielded loop antenna.

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heterodyne receivers [6]. Nonetheless, research has highlighted that measurement results may deviate due to the mutual coupling (MC) effect of the MSLA construction, requiring considerations to resolve differences between the standard SLA and the MSLA configuration [8]. To counteract this effect, investigating the correction factor technique for MC is necessary.

To maintain the measurement time under control, standards also limit EV operational mode evaluations. The fixed laboratory measurement conditions, as standardized by CISPR 36, are effective and efficient in creating a repeatable test setup. However, the condition where the EV operates at a fixed speed of 60 km/h could be improved to better represent the real operational modes of EV in daily urban driving patterns. An investigation in [9] on different driving stages in the city revealed that a speed of 60 km/h over a 38.5 km path was only briefly reached a few times, as shown in Fig. 2. Most driving conditions involved acceleration from 10 to 40-50 km/h and braking stages. This highlights the oversimplification of driving conditions evaluated by the standard for the sake of repeatability. In [4], an investigation of different driving conditions such as acceleration, deceleration, switch-on, and gear setting was conducted. The results showed that acceleration from 0 to 40 km/h exhibited 5 to 16 dB higher emissions over the frequency range than the 60 km/h static driving mode required by the basic measurements [4]. Because of this, investigating real operational conditions and not just fixed operational speeds is necessary for better understanding the emission profile of modern EV. Fig. 2 and the report [9] show that acceleration lasts over 3 to 5 seconds, but the measurement time described in CISPR 36 requirements is limited to 50 ms with a peak detector pre-scan method and 1 second with a quasi-peak detector measurement method. This measurement dwell time is insufficient to capture several seconds of time-variant emissions.

Addressing these challenges with strict requirements using a single SLA and CISPR 36 measurement techniques would require weeks or months to evaluate EV operational modes. This is due to the fact that for each frequency step measurement conditions of the time-vary operational modes should stay the same. Therefore, it is imperative to investigate a new measurement approach that can address dynamic operational modes and reduce the time required for a complete EV

Fig. 2 Comparison of speed and acceleration of the 38.5 km total length of the path [9].

evaluation. For this reason, it is crucial to explore a new measurement approach that transitions from frequency domain (FD) to time domain (TD), as this can significantly reduce evaluation time by capturing all spectrum components at once and allowing for extended recording of time-variant operational modes that exceed dwell time, which the FD approach fails to capture effectively [10], [11].

In this paper, the proposed MSLA is described in Section II, covering the MSLA construction and its effect on the magnetic field response. Section III presents the method for measuring MC between antennas in the MSLA construction. In Section IV, the MC correction factor compensation method is introduced, along with a comparison of measurements between a single antenna construction and the MSLA. Finally, Section V discusses potential improvements to further optimize the measurement procedure.

II. MULTI-AXIS SHIELDED LOOP ANTENNA

The following sections cover the MSLA construction and the influence of the close proximity effect of antennas in the MSLA on antenna factor (AF) deviation.

A. MSLA construction

The MSLA construction used in this study is depicted in Fig. 1. This construction consists of three shielded loop antennas nested within each other. To combine them, diameters of 57 cm ($MSLA_Y$), 60 cm ($MSLA_X$), and 63 cm ($MSLA_Z$) for the shielded loop antennas were selected. This antenna construction ensures the alignment of the central point of all loops and removes any offset that could occur if all antennas had the same diameter. Each loop is detachable, which allows to characterize their AF both individually and as a whole MSLA construction itself. The orthogonal orientations of the antennas maximize the cross-polarization isolation [12], [13], yet does not entirely eliminate the coupling due to their physical imperfections effected in any construction of this kind. Fig. 3 shows the round mold for antennas building process.

Fig. 3 Round mold for antenna building process.

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This round mold can be adjusted for any required antenna diameter. Within this round mold, 12 mm wrapped insulated copper tube was positioned to create a circle. A copper T-piece was inserted to create an exit from the loop for the copper wire, which will be fed inside the tube. After soldering the inner conductor wire can be installed. Choosing a 60 cm diameter loop antenna provides a practical balance between size and performance: it remains electrically small (well within 1/5 of the 30 MHz), stays below its self-resonance in the frequency range of interest, and provides a higher sensitivity for the low-frequency range. It is also important to note that SLA is highly sensitive to the angle of the magnetic field lines that are crossing its effective area. Rotating the antennas by 90 degrees relative to each other is a straightforward and effective strategy to reduce interference between MSLA and to meet the standards requirement for evaluating three planes from a single antenna position [5]. In Table I the physical properties of the MSLA are shown.

B. AF measurements

To investigate the influence on the AF, the MSLA was deconstructed, and individual antenna AF measurements were performed [14]. These measurements serve as a reference to show deviations in AF between individual antennas and when they are assembled into the MSLA construction. In this paper, a traceable loop antenna calibration method using a vector-network analyzer was implemented to calibrate the antennas [15]. The three-loop antenna calibration method, as referenced in [16], requires three individual loop antennas, which are measured in a specific order to calculate the AF for each. To avoid the influence of human error during the measurement procedure, two additional SLAs with a 60 cm diameter were used as reference antennas. Over all measurements the difference in the AFs for the reference antennas did not exceed a deviation of 0.05 dB. Because of this the difference in the AF for individual antenna from MSLA and an assembled MSLA construction is caused solely by its construction.

Fig. 4 represents the measurement procedure for one disassembled shielded loop antenna used for X-axis measurements in the MSLA construction. The same procedure was repeated for each antenna after assembling the MSLA. Fig. 5 shows one of the three measurements for the MSLA_Y antenna.

The distance between the centres of the antennas was 1 m, and the distance between the ground and the antenna centre was 1.3 m [1]. This distance between the antennas was used to minimize the influence of the conducting walls in the chamber, where the distance to the walls should be twice the distance between the antennas.

Table I Multi-axis shielded loop antenna construction specification

Antenna diameter (cm)	Inner conductor length (cm)	Area (cm ²)	Air gap in shield (mm)	Outer diameter of the tube (mm)	Inner diameter of the tube (mm)	Tube wall thickness (mm)
57	180	2551	4	12	10	1
60	189	2827	4	12	10	1
63	199	3117	4	12	10	1

Fig. 4 Three-antennas calibration setup for a single antenna from the MSLA construction. In this case demonstrated for the antenna which is responsible for the X-axis in the MSLA.

C. Measurement results.

Fig. 5 Three-antennas calibration setup for the MSLA. The measurement for the Y antenna in the MSLA.

The AF for the single antennas and assembled MSLA construction are shown in Fig. 6. The AF differences for individual antennas and the MSLA configuration, shown in Fig. 7, fall within the range of -0.1 to 0.45 dB. From these results, it can be concluded that the influence of the MSLA on the axial magnetic field component response is low.

However, as shown in [6], the measurement error can increase significantly for the response of the non-dominant antennas that are influenced by the radial magnetic field component. This occurs for several reasons, such as the antenna construction locally disturbing the field due to imperfect alignment of loops and scattering effects. In the next section, this is shown as MC between antennas.

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Fig. 6 AF for each antenna in MSLA and SLA construction.

Fig. 7 Difference in the AF between SLA and MSLA.

III. MSLA MC MEASUREMENTS

In this section, the measurement technique for MC between antennas in the MSLA, along with the measurement results, are introduced.

A. MSLA MC measurement method

The MC is expressed here as the S21 parameter measured by the VNA, as shown in Fig. 8. The antenna not connected to the

Fig. 8 S21 measurement setup for a MSLA construction.

VNA was loaded with 50 Ohms to maintain its loading conditions as if it were connected to a receiver. Due to the fact that only MSLA will be used further in the formulas and graphs to reduce complexity, 'MSLA_X' will be referred to as 'X', 'MSLA_Y' as 'Y', and 'MSLA_Z' as 'Z', as shown in Fig. 8. Measurements of the combinations between antennas X&Y, X&Z, Y&Z in an MSLA construction give the results of the reradiation magnetic field, which will occur during the actual measurements.

B. MSLA MC measurement results

Measurement results show that the MC between each antenna in the proposed MSLA construction with different antenna diameters is relatively low, as visualized in Fig. 9 (a) and Fig. 10 (a). The linear scale for the figures was chosen due to the fact that the MC is dominant at the higher frequencies. The highest measured MC was at a frequency of 30 MHz, reaching around -37 dB. The difference of the MC measurement results between Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 is caused by deconstruction and assembling antenna again. Even if the antenna was assembled in the same way as it was before the mutual coupling between antennas can change, since even a small deviation in the antennas placements will result in a, very small, different MC.

The phase relation from the S21 parameter between antennas

Fig. 9 MC measurement results a) amplitude and b) phase behaviour.

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is shown in Fig. 9 (b) and Fig. 10 (b). Further, the measured phase shift and the level of the coupled signal will be used for the MC correction factor implementation. Due to this in Section IV the MC coefficients will be presented by the $k_{XY}(f)$ factor which is taken from the S21 measurements and represent the amplitude scaling factor from one antenna to another antenna and the phase shift of the coupled signal with respect to the injected signal. Each frequency step from 150 kHz to 30 MHz has its own k coefficient.

Moreover, in [17], a deeper discussion on the complexity of measuring the Z-axis magnetic field component is presented. The research theoretically and practically demonstrates that when the magnetic field is measured around the EV, with the main lobe directed towards the roof of the EV along the Z-axis, the measurement results will be approximately 15 dB lower compared to the lobes directed towards the sides of the EV along the X and Y axes. Furthermore, different MSLA constructions can significantly alter the MC between antennas, potentially showing much higher MC than what was reported in this paper for the MSLA depicted in Fig. 1. Due to this, even if the MSLA construction does not significantly impact the AF, considering the MC between antennas becomes essential for MSLA measurements, especially in the Z-axis.

Fig. 10 MC measurement results a) amplitude and b) phase behaviour.

IV. MC CORRECTION FACTOR

In this section the numerical approach for the MC correction factor and the implementation of it are shown.

A. Numerical approach

By implementing a multi-channel digitizer the amplitude and the phase difference between each antenna in MSLA simultaneous measured over the time. When a short-time FFT is applied to the digitized time-domain signals during post-processing, both the amplitude and phase of each frequency component can be accurately tracked as functions of frequency (f) and time (τ). In this work, the MC coefficients $k_{XY}(f)$, $k_{XZ}(f)$ and $k_{YZ}(f)$ are considered to be only frequency-dependent, while the measured signals $X'(\tau, f)$, $Y'(\tau, f)$ and $Z'(\tau, f)$ acquire time dependence through the STFT segmentation. Consequently, each digitizer port receives a combination of the desired signal from its corresponding antenna and the contributions coupled from the other two antennas at each τ and f , expressed as:

$$X'(\tau, f) = X(\tau, f) + k_{XY}(f) \cdot Y(\tau, f) + k_{XZ}(f) \cdot Z(\tau, f) \quad (1)$$

$$Y'(\tau, f) = Y(\tau, f) + k_{XY}(f) \cdot X(\tau, f) + k_{YZ}(f) \cdot Z(\tau, f) \quad (2)$$

$$Z'(\tau, f) = Z(\tau, f) + k_{YZ}(f) \cdot Y(\tau, f) + k_{XZ}(f) \cdot X(\tau, f) \quad (3)$$

where $X'(\tau, f)$, $Y'(\tau, f)$ and $Z'(\tau, f)$ are the signals measured on the three digitizer ports corresponding to $X(\tau, f)$, $Y(\tau, f)$ and $Z(\tau, f)$ magnetic field components, and $k_{XY}(f)$, $k_{XZ}(f)$ and $k_{YZ}(f)$ are the MC coefficients. The coefficients are obtained from the S21 parameter measurements shown in the previous section. Since the antennas interact with each other, the above set of equations forms a system of three unknowns at each time–frequency bin (τ, f).

To find the original signals the matrix form is used. The matrix of coefficients is denoted as $M(f)$. The equation (1) - (3) can then be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X'(\tau, f) \\ Y'(\tau, f) \\ Z'(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} = M \cdot \begin{bmatrix} X(\tau, f) \\ Y(\tau, f) \\ Z(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$M(f) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & k_{XY}(f) & k_{XZ}(f) \\ k_{XY}(f) & 1 & k_{YZ}(f) \\ k_{XZ}(f) & k_{YZ}(f) & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

To find the original signals X, Y and Z two matrixes should be multiplied:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X(\tau, f) \\ Y(\tau, f) \\ Z(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} = M(f)^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} X'(\tau, f) \\ Y'(\tau, f) \\ Z'(\tau, f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

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Solving this matrix equation at each τ (time slice) and f (frequency bin) provides the original signals, removing the effect of mutual coupling through the entire measurement process.

B. Measurement setup

To validate the proposed compensation method, a MSLA and a multichannel digitizer are used. Given that the noise floor of the digitizer approached the threshold specified by the CISPR 36 standard for upper frequencies between 20 and 30 MHz, low-noise preamplifiers were used between the antenna and the digitizer [18]. Preamplifiers were validated to not introduce any phase shifts. Fig. 11 shows the measurement setup. As a digitizer a PicoScope® 5444D MSO model was used [19]. The MSLA was connected to channels A, B, and C, respectively. A sampling frequency of 125 MS/s was chosen, that is four times higher than the highest measured frequency, to improve accuracy. The resolution of the digitizer was set to 8-bit. The software part for data gathering and post processing was written in Python. A magnetic field source was a shielded loop antenna facing the MSLA at a certain angle, specifically not aligned with any antenna in the MSLA construction, therefore generating all three X, Y, Z field components.

From Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, the highest MC effect between antennas can be found at 30 MHz. Due to this, the 30 MHz frequency was chosen for the first measurement to validate the MC correction factor technique. The second set of measurements, aimed at showing deviations in the measurement results around the equipment under test (EUT), covered the entire frequency range from 150 kHz to 30 MHz, comparing a single SLA to the MSLA setup. To achieve this, a signal containing peaks at every 200 kHz was used.

Fig. 11 Measurement setup: multi-axis antenna, preamplifier, digitizer, laptop.

C. Validation for 30 MHz

The SLA used as the emission source and was positioned in a way that it emitted a high level of magnetic field in one axis, a smaller level in the second, and the lowest in the third [6]. This is one of the cases investigated in [6], which showed a high deviation in the measurement results of the antenna that picked up the lowest magnetic field level. Fig. 11 demonstrates the effectiveness and importance of this MC correction technique. In Fig. 12 each 3 bars represent measurement plane. The first bar in each 3 bars represent measurements with MSLA without

implementation of the MC correction factor, the second reference measurement with a SLA, and the third one result of the MSLA measurement with implementation of the MC correction factor. In scenarios with high measurement signal of 55 dB μ A/m in the Z-axis (first 3 bars in the Fig. 12) and 31 dB μ A/m in the X-axis (second 3 bars in the Fig. 12), the outcomes remain remarkably consistent for SLA and MSLA with and without MC correction factor implementation. It is due to the fact that the magnetic field level on both of these antennas is comparable high and the MC connection will not have a significant impact on them. This consistency is due to the proposed antenna design that shows a low level of the MC coefficients (Fig. 9 and Fig. 10).

However, a weakest measurement results initially measured at 19.5 dB μ A/m in the Y-axis is influenced by the MSLA MC effect between XY and YZ antennas. With the implementation of the MC correction factor, the lowest level which was measured by the MSLA become consistent with the measurement results obtained by the SLA (last 2 bars Fig. 12) and start to correspond to 14 dB μ A/m.

This scenario highlights the effectiveness of the proposed compensation method, as the MSLA construction amplifies the signal due to MC effects. However, if the phase shift between received signals on each axis differs, the MSLA may suppress the signal, leading to an underestimation of the MC level on one axis. By integrating the proposed MC correction factor with the standard antenna factor, high measurement precision is achieved, even for low-level signals, allowing the use of MSLA in other construction implementations, despite a possible stronger MC effects between antennas.

Fig. 12 Amplitude response for 30 MHz. Single antenna measurements in combination with MSLA with and without MC correction factor.

D. Measurement results around an EUT.

To verify the effectiveness of this method across the entire frequency spectrum, the TX shielded loop antenna was angled

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and treated as an 'unidentified' magnetic field source. The EUT, in this case, a tilted SLA, was measured 12 times from different positions and orientation which is described in the standard method and 4 times with the proposed measurement method. The outcomes of these measurements are presented in Fig. 13. Standards for magnetic field measurements typically concentrate on the highest level of emissions detected. Hence, the presentation of the measurement results highlighted the peak value from each axis across the four measurements positions.

The measurement results indicate a high degree of precision between the single shield loop antenna and the MSLA, with a minor deviation in peak measurement results of approximately 0.3-0.4 dB. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the measurement setup employing the MSLA is not only comparable to the standard measurement method but also offers advantages in terms of time savings and the capability to measure transient processes by the data recording which is provided by the digitizer.

V. DISCUSSION

Despite advantages, the MSLA system faces challenges related to the MC effect between antennas in the MSLA construction, which can introduce errors, particularly for the low-level measured signals. Without proper correction, these errors can lead to significant deviations in the measurement results. The MC correction factor which was shown in this paper significantly reduces any influence of the MSLA construction on the measurement results.

Enabling high measurement accuracy that competes with the standard SLA construction, further integration of the measurement methods is possible. In [20], the implementation of several multi-channel digitizers was demonstrated. By using

synchronization and time stamps on the TD data, multiple multi-channel digitizers can be combined with several MSLA units placed around an EUT. This also allows higher sampling rates, and thus oversampling, which can increase the signal to noise ratio. Due to the relatively low cost of modern digitizers compared to multi-channel TD EMI receivers, the advantage of a such technique is high. Fig. 14 shows the possible implementations of multiple MSLA units.

Such a measurement setup, supported by the MC correction factor, can significantly decrease the evaluation time of the EUT. It enables tracking of the phase shift between each axis across the four measurement positions required by the standards simultaneously. Access to both the amplitude and phase behaviour around an EUT can provide valuable insights to development personnel on how to mitigate the outgoing magnetic field from the EUT, improving overall measurement efficiency and accuracy.

Fig. 14 Implementation of multiple digitizers in combination with several MSLA around the EUT.

Fig. 13 Measurement results around an EUT. The max hold of the four different positions around the EUT is presented for three antenna orientations, using both an SLA and an MSLA with the MC correction method.

VI. CONCLUSION

The MSLA construction combined with a multichannel digitizer represents a significant advancement in magnetic field measurements below 30 MHz. This innovative system evaluates all antenna orientations simultaneously, reducing measurement time drastically compared to traditional methods that use a single SLA (and a single-input conventional super-heterodyne receivers). By employing a MSLA and multichannel TD measurements, the proposed measurement method provides comprehensive access to all three axes and additional phase shift information, resulting in enhanced measurement accuracy and mitigating the limitations of conventional single-axis measurement approaches.

Implementing an advanced MSLA MC correction factor which is shown in this research, achieves extreme accuracy in measurement results. While different antenna constructions can significantly vary the MC between antennas, the proposed correction method effectively mitigates these variations, allowing even non-ideal MSLA constructions to be used in measurement procedures.

The combination of the MSLA with multi-channel measurements using modern digitizers can reduce standard measurement times from hours to mere seconds. This innovation allows for more ideal measurement procedures, enabling evaluations based not only on single operational modes but also on real-world urban driving patterns without significantly increasing measurement time.

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2022 Richard B. Shultz Best Transaction Paper Award of IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility for the journal paper entitled: "Susceptibility of Static Energy Meters Due to Amplifier Clipping Caused by a Rogowski Coil.

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